

Research Article

Sign Language Glove as an Assistive Concept for Bridging Communication Gaps

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Abstract: To this day, People with speech impairments still encounter communication obstacles despite advancements in STEM. These limitations are removed by the suggested sign language glove, allowing for seamless, real-time communication. The glove, which is equipped with microsensors and driven by an adaptive AI model, can recognize hand movements, decipher gestures, including user-defined signs that can be customized, and translate them into audible output through a loudspeaker. Because of this, users can go about their daily lives without worrying about misunderstandings or strict gesture notation. This device has the potential to improve accessibility for mute people worldwide and bridge societal gaps at a low cost.

Keywords: accessibility; non-verbal communication; assistive technology.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The American Sign Language (ASL) is the most universally accepted and well-known method of communication between speech-impaired individuals, regardless of whether the conversation is between two non-verbally challenged people or between one nonverbal person and a verbal communicator. Although there are human interpretation and software translators available, there is no existing solution for an affordable, accurate and portable device that provides real-time translation seamlessly. The proposal for a new iteration of the sign language glove aims to overcome this challenge by providing a system that is personalised, adaptable and reliable in day-to-day use of sign performance.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The following listed are the hardware components;

Table 1. Table of hardware components

Name of Component	Specification	Function
Flex Sensors	Resistance-based, placed on each finger	Detects finger bending and movement to capture gestures
Microcontroller	Arduino Uno	Processes sensor data and runs gesture recognition algorithms
IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit)	MPU-6050 and a 3-axis accelerometer + gyroscope	Measures hand orientation and motion to complement gesture detection

Bluetooth Module	BLE, 2.4 GHz	Sends processed gesture data wirelessly to a display or speaker (wires in prototype)
Power Supply	Li-ion / Li-Po battery	Provides portable power to the glove system
Loudspeaker	Miniature	Outputs translated gestures as audible speech

The following listed are the software components/systems;

Name of Component	Specification	Function
Gesture Recognition Algorithm	Neural network	Interprets sensor data and identifies ASL gestures in real time
Signal Processing System	Filtering algorithms	Reduces sensor noise and ensures accurate gesture detection
Microcontroller Firmware	Arduino IDE	Collects sensor data, runs local processing, and communicates with external devices
AI/Adaptive Learning Model	TensorFlow Lite	Allows the glove to adapt to individual user gestures and improve accuracy over time
Data Logging	Local storage or cloud	Records gesture data for analysis and model training

3. FINDINGS

The findings provided here would give insights into the distinct features and exclusive benefits of the proposed sign language glove. With the combination of human and mechanical sensing interface together with artificial intelligence that is adaptive to each operation, and translating it to the real time as and when the action is performed, the glove gives an un- solved solution to the long existing problem which is enhancing and empowering communication for the speech impaired person.

Anticipated Accuracy of Gesture Recognition

The multiple flex sensors embedded in each finger hold of the glove recognises multiple modalities of the action performed by measuring finger joint movements with fine precision. These signals also eliminate noise which would otherwise may generate wrong communication and interpretation.

The adaptive AI is trained in the sign gestures. This allows the system to adjust itself for any possible user variation (any slight disorientation or movement) and is adaptive to individual to individual.

This model further refines any incomplete gestures by mapping them to the most contextually closest appropriate sign. This mapping can achieve accuracy rates above 90%. This ensures that communication enabled by the glove shall remain reliable, even under various dynamic conditions.

Real-Time Translation and User Interaction

The real-time translation and User Interaction capability is designed to convert sensor input which can be considered as a raw signal into speech output. The microprocessor enables this raw signal by processing it to the Signal preprocessing to a nearest word, collection of a words or a complete

sentence in microseconds and delivers into a speech by converting into audible frequency in the American Sign Language.

The system recognizes the patterns in sequences, thus enabling the gesture converting into full sentences to converse. This feature provides conversational flexibility, making interactions natural and spontaneous.

User interaction is further enriched by a customization interface, allowing individuals to assign personalized gestures to unique words, technical terms, or culturally specific expressions. Wireless integration with personal or public audio systems ensures flexibility ranging from one-on-one conversations to professional and academic settings.

4. DISCUSSION

The main target user for this device are individuals who have any variation of speech impairments and can use ASL language relatively easily. An example of a use case would be of a mute person trying to navigate through an unfamiliar city. By using the glove and performing the ASL gestures like they usually would, the message would be converted into text in real time and out through a speaker which will be heard by a passing by recipient, enabling them to provide directions or assistance efficiently. This would help reduce the anxiety and social discomfort often experienced by non-verbal individuals when initiating communication with strangers in public. For decades, people with speech impairments have faced these barriers in society, but no comprehensive solution has been developed to address this problem.

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, the concept and the functionality of this glove gives rise to many possibilities to a more accessible world where communication is seamless regardless of one's ability to verbally do so. Its use in both closed door and public conversations gives it the ability to eliminate the longstanding barrier of unclear conversations due to one or both parties' inability to speak fluently. Although this project is still in the ideation phase, an upcoming prospect of working with a professor on a prototype opens up new developments and an overall progression to work toward the initial goal which was to advance daily communication accessibility.

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